

Tertiary Education Trust Fund Utilization and Academic Staff Effectiveness in Tertiary Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria

Ebri Emmanuel Obono^{1*}, Eteng Eyong Uren²

¹Cross River State College of Education, Akamkpa.

²Department of Educational Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

* Corresponding Author

Email: ebrie@yahoo.com

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5624990

Abstract

The study investigates the influence of Tertiary Education Trust Fund Utilization in Staff and infrastructural development on academic staff effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. Two research questions and null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A survey research design was used in the study. The population of the study include all the tertiary institutions in the state that are under the Ministry of Education. All the two hundred and seven two (272) academic staff in administrative positions were selected purposively and used in the study as respondents. An instrument titled "Tertiary Education Trust Fund Utilization and Academic Staff Effectiveness Questionnaire (TETFUNDUASEQ)" was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was validated by three experts. Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure the reliability coefficient of the instrument after a pilot test was conducted. The data collection exercise was done by the researchers. Simple regression was used to analyse the data. The result of the analysis revealed that TETFUND utilization in staff and infrastructural development has signification influence on the academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that TETFUND should be utilized appropriately to enhance academic staff effectiveness for tertiary education goals attainment.

Keywords: Academic staff, effectiveness, infrastructural development, staff development, TETFUND

Cite as: Obono, E. E., & Uren, E. E. (2021). Tertiary education trust fund utilisation and academic staff effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning & Research*, 13(1), 139-146. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5624990>

Introduction

Tertiary institutions are institutions of higher learning that trains individuals to acquire high-level relevant skills for national development. They include; universities, polytechnics, monotechnics and colleges of Education. The purpose of tertiary institutions in Nigeria is to pursue tertiary education goals as contained in the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004), which among other goals include, contributing to national development through high-level relevant manpower training. The fulfilment of tertiary education goals depends to a large extent on the effectiveness of the academic staff who perform teaching and research functions of tertiary

institutions. The academic staff teaches students to acquire skills and knowledge in their areas of specializations and also undertakes researches to generate ideas and contribute to their institutional research profile. Effectiveness refers to how well a task is being carried out or perform to achieve the desired outcome. It is the ability to carry out particular tasks successfully. From an academic staff standpoint, effectiveness is the ability of the academic staff to perform their duties or tasks in a way that will ensure the attainment of school goals.

Academic staff effectiveness is significant and remains the major factor that determines the success of any educational institution. Nicholl in Uko (2014) stated that the success of any education system depends largely upon the quality of both teaching and non-teaching staff and upon the effectiveness with which they discharge their duties. The government are constantly making efforts aimed at improving the effectiveness of the academic staff. Apart from the yearly allocation of budget to educational institutions, the Federal Government of Nigeria has set aside tertiary education intervention funds known as Tertiary Education Trust Funds (TETFUND) to support tertiary institutions in Nigeria in some critical areas. TETFUND is generated through the two per cent educational tax imposed on the accessible profits of all the registered multi-national companies in Nigeria, through the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) TETFUND is managed by the Board of Trustees and the Secretariat. The Board of Trustees is made up of eleven members drawn from the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria, as well as representatives of the Federal Ministries of Education and finance, and the Federal Inland Revenue Service. The secretariat is headed by the Executive Secretary who is the chief accounting officer of the TETFUND. The secretariat also has Directors and Heads of units who assist the Executive Secretary in the daily administration of the TETFUND. The mandate of the management as contained in the TETFUND Act 2011, is to support tertiary institutions in Nigeria by utilizing TETFUND in areas which in its opinion are critical and essential in improving academic staff effectiveness for quality tertiary education (TETFUND, 2011). Among the areas where TETFUND is utilized in tertiary institutions include staff and infrastructural development.

Staff development is the process of designing and implementing programmes that will impart knowledge and skills to the employees of an organisation to enable them to carry out their duties effectively, Ochai and Osuji, (2011) defined staff development as a process of providing skills and knowledge which brings about desired outcome and enhances the competence of the employees. Nwaham, Chukwuma and Ajudiamu (2011) viewed staff development as an opportunity given to teachers to improve on their job performance which eventually affects the quality of students they produce. Nwangwu and Igbo (2011) defined staff development as an all-embracing professional development that addresses inadequacies of pre-service training of the teachers. On his part, Akpan (2011) viewed staff development as involving the process of developing skills, learning concepts, rules and attitudes to improve the standard of performance of the workers. Changes in technologies, methodologies and techniques of teaching require that academic staff must constantly be developed to update their skills and knowledge to suit these changes. Adequate job performance or changes resulting from job redesigning or declined in productivity or technological breakthrough requires some types of development programmes for the workers. Staff development programmes enhance

workers effectiveness and organizational output (Manoria & Ganker, 2010). Idoli (2012) reports that staff development has an absolute positive connection with academic staff output. According to the author, academic staff output depended among other things on the acquisition of skills, knowledge and experiences which is attributed to staff development programmes. No wonder Uko (2014) warned that except teachers are properly trained to acquire new skills and update their knowledge, they cannot live up to expectations because they cannot give what they do not have.

Infrastructural development on the other hand is the process of putting in place all the basic facilities that the school requires to junction effectively. They include those physical facilities that make the school environment conducive for teaching and learning, such as office space, classroom buildings or blocks, water, access roads, electricity, laboratory equipment among others. Infrastructural facilities play a vital role in academic staff effectiveness. For instance, modern teaching requires the use of some sort of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities which in turn requires electricity to operate them. No matter amount of training received by academic staff, when there are no facilities to operate with, they cannot function effectively for the attainment of educational goals. Efiabung (2010) noted that an appropriate level of infrastructural facilities is necessary for improving teachers' effectiveness and quality of education in Nigeria Universities. Ndugu (2014) revealed that teachers' effectiveness and productivity depend on several factors such as teaching qualification, teaching experience and infrastructures that are put in place. Chimaka, long and Shaibu (2009) observed that declined in staff effectiveness is a result of obsolete teaching and research facilities.

Similarly, Odekunle in Obono (2015) pointed out that the deficiency in infrastructural development in Nigerian universities has created problems in the areas of teaching, accommodation, reduction in space per student and dilapidated classrooms laboratories and equipment. Fagge (2013) revealed that Nigeria Universities are performing below average when compared to other Universities in Africa because there are no supporting facilities to enhance teachers' effectiveness. In the same vein, Evarista (2009) maintained that the deplorable state of infrastructural facilities in public Universities is a major setback to achieving the goals of tertiary education in Nigeria. Academic staff requires a well-furnished conducive office, electricity, functional classrooms and well-equipped laboratory were necessary to function effectively for the achievement of educational goals. When these are lacking, they cannot function effectively to achieve the desired result. From the foregoing, it can be suggested that staff and infrastructural development enhances effectiveness. It is based on this that this study was conceived to find out whether TETFUND utilization for staff and infrastructural development has any influence on academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Academic staff effectiveness is a measure of how well academic staff have been able to carry out their duties. It is one of the determinants of tertiary education goals attainment, when

academic staff are not effective, the goals of tertiary education remain unattainable. Reports from many researchers revealed that the effectiveness of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Nigeria is below expectation when compared to other academic staff in tertiary institutions outside Nigeria in terms of teaching and research. For instance, Ekpela in Idoli (2012) reported that there is a low level of research publication and ineffective teaching among academic staff in Nigeria. These accounted for the low level of the research profile of many tertiary institutions and the poor academic performance of students. These problems may be attributed to a lack of staff development programmes to update academic staff with new knowledge and skills in their areas of specialization and inadequate infrastructures for meaningful teaching and research. It is against the backdrop of academic staff ineffectiveness occasioned by lack of adequate staff and infrastructural development that TETFUND is utilized in this regard. Regrettably, despite TETFUND utilization over the year, the problem of academic staff ineffectiveness persists. Hence, the question of whether TETFUND utilization for staff and infrastructural development influences academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions in Cross River State, necessitated this study.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. TETFUND utilization in staff development does not have any significant influence on the academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions.
2. There is no significant influence of TETFUND utilization in infrastructural development on the academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions.

Methods

A survey research design was adopted in the study. The study was carried out in the Cross River State of Nigeria. The state is one of the six states in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It is situated within the Niger region of the country. The state has boundaries with Benue State to the North, Akwa Ibom State and the Atlantic Ocean to the South Ebonyi and the Abia States to the West and Republic of Cameroon to the East. The state has many tertiary institutions. The population of the study include all the four tertiary institutions in the state that are under the Ministry of Education. They include the University of Calabar, Cross River State University of Technology, Federal College of Education and Cross River State College of Education.

All the two hundred and seventy-two (272) Deans of faculties, Heads of Departments and Directors of Academic Programmes were selected purposively as respondents in the study. An instrument titled Tertiary Education Trust Fund Utilization and Academic Staff Effectiveness Questionnaire (TETFUNDUASEQ) was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was validated by three experts who made some modifications in the items to suit the purpose of the instrument. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot-test was conducted using thirty Deans of Faculties, Heads of Departments and Directors of Academic Programme from Tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. Data generated were

subjected to test of reliability using Cronbach's Alpha method and returned a reliability estimate of 0.78 and 0.81 which is considered reliable for used in the study. Data collection exercise was carried out by the researchers, out of 272 questionnaires distributed 266 were successfully retrieved and used for the analysis. Simple regression was used to analyse the data at the .05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

TETFUND utilization in staff development does not have any significant influence on the academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions. The result of this hypothesis is presented in table 1. The analysis in table I indicated that Adj. R^2 is .047. This implies that 5% of the variance in the dependent variable (Academic staff effectiveness) could be accounted for by TETFUND utilization in staff development in tertiary institutions. Though, the percentage contribution was small. A good look at the table indicated that ($F = 36.633$, $P < .05$). since $P(000)$ is less than $P(.05)$, it means that TETFUND utilization in staff development has a significant influence on academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 1: Simple regression analysis of the influence of TETFUND utilization in staff development on academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions (N = 266).

Variable	R	R^2	Adj. R^{2E}	Std. Error	
Academic staff effectiveness	.23	0.48	.05	4.13	
Source of variance	SS	Df	Ms	F	Sig
Regression	322.12	1	312.43	36.63*	.00
Residual	12283.43	264	18.16		
Total	12605.55	265			

*Significant at $P < .05$ level.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of TETFUND utilization in infrastructural development on the academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions. The result of this hypothesis is presented in table 2. The analysis in table 2 shows that the Adj. R^2 is .04. This implies that 4% of the variance in the dependent variable (Academic staff effectiveness) could be accounted for by TETFUND for infrastructural development in tertiary institutions. Although the percentage contribution was small. According to the table ($F = 19.64$, $P < .05$). since $p(.00)$ is less than the alpha level of .05, it means that there is a significant influence of TETFUND utilization for infrastructural development on academic staff effectiveness with the result, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 2: Simple regression analysis of the influence of TETFUND utilization in infrastructural development on academic staff effectiveness of tertiary institutions (N = 266)

Variable	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std. Error	
Academic staff effectiveness	.36	.05	.04	4.23	
Source of variance	SS	Df	Ms	F	Sig.
Regression	270.34	1	185.13	19.64*	.00
Residual	12335.55	264	14.43		
Total	12605.89	265			

*Significance at P <.05 level.

Discussion

The result of hypothesis one shows that TETFUND utilization for staff development has a significant influence on academic staff effectiveness. This result is in line with the finding of Idoli (2012) who discovered that staff development has an absolute positive connection with academic staff output. The author also reports that academic staff output depended among other things on the acquisition of skills, knowledge and experiences which are attributed to the staff development programme. Similarly, the finding agrees with Mamoria and Ganker (2010) who also reports that staff development programmes enhance workers effectiveness and organisational output. TETFUND utilization for staff development enhances academic staff effectiveness by exposing them to various development programmes which impart new knowledge and skills necessary for their job performance.

The result of hypothesis two also revealed that there is a significant influence of TETFUND utilization infrastructural development on academic staff effectiveness. The result reaffirmed Ndugu (2014) who stated that teachers' effectiveness and productivity depend on several factors which among them is infrastructural facilities that are put in place. Efibung (2010) also vital that an appropriate level of infrastructural facilities is necessary for improving teachers' effectiveness and quality of education in Nigerian universities. The result also confirmed Chiamaka, Long and Shaibu (2009) who disclosed that a decline in staff effectiveness is a result of obsolete teaching and research facilities. Fagge (2013) revealed that Nigeria universities are performing below average when compared with other universities in Africa because there are no supporting facilities to enhance teachers' effectiveness, TETFUND utilization for infrastructural development is a landmark for improving academic staff effectiveness in a tertiary institution. Training becomes ineffective when academic staff are not provided with the necessary facilities to enhance their job effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that TETFUND utilization for staff and infrastructural development enhances the job effectiveness of academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. TETFUND should always be utilized appropriately to enhance academic staff job effectiveness.
2. Academic staff should always be encouraged to participate in staff development programmes sponsored by TETFUND to acquire new skills and knowledge necessary in improving their job effectiveness.
3. TETFUND funding for infrastructural development in tertiary institutions should be a continuous process to enhance academic staff job effectiveness.

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